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Title: FRESHMAN COLLEGE STUDENTS' EXTENT OF KNOWLEDGE, SKILLS, AND DISPOSITIONS ON CIVIC ENGAGEMENT: TOWARDS NURTURING SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the extent of knowledge, skills, and dispositions of the freshman students on civic engagement. The study employed quantitative-qualitative research design. In the quantitative approach, descriptive-comparative technique was used to describe the extent of knowledge, skills, and dispositions of the freshman students on civic engagement and to determine the relationship among the variables. The research tool used for this study was adopted from the Civic Engagement Survey which was developed during the spring 2008 semester by the Southwest Minnesota State University (SMSU). The study also employed qualitative method to surface responses which were used to provide in-depth discussion through open ended interview guide questions. The respondents of the study were the first year students from the School of Accountancy and Business, School of Health and Natural Sciences, School of Teacher Education and Humanities, and School of Engineering, Architecture, and Information Technology. Finding showed that the freshman students' extent of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement was moderate. Moreover, socio-economic status affect the freshman students' extent of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement. This implies that there is a need to strengthen this particular concern through activities that will help nurture the students' civic engagement. The study further recommends enhancing students' knowledge, skills and dispositions to civic engagement through the provision of activities such as classroom and co-curricular and extra-curricular.

Keywords: *Age, community project, religious affiliationservice learning, sex, socio- economic status*

Introduction

Vital to the health of individual wellbeing as well as to democratic societies is the presence of actively engaged and informed populace. Through civic engagement, individuals' values, skills, attitudes, and behaviors are geared towards helpful contributions to community. Civic engagement, as one of the recognized duties of citizens, incorporates as sense of responsibility among citizens with the primary aim of making positive change in one's local community as well as the worldwide community. As indicated in the study of Nava, Agustin, & Catacutan, (2021), through engagement in civic activities, social justice is

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advanced and the wellbeing of people and their quality of life are promoted. However, the study of Bermudez (2012) pointed to the seemingly global decline of youth civic engagement. As indicated in the study, youth worldwide “exhibited growing apathy, a loss of interest in civic and political affairs, an avoidance of electoral and other democratic responsibilities, and little investment in community wellbeing”. This situation prompted insistent and growing concern in civic engagement.

As defined in the study of Owusu-Agyeman & Fourie-Malherbe (2021), civic engagement refers to “working to make a difference in the civic life of our communities and developing the combination of knowledge, skills, values, and motivations to make that difference”. Youth civic engagement is important in order to transform society and uphold social justice. In relation to this, the World Youth Report (WYR) as a flagship publication of the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA), Division for Inclusive Social Development (DISD) presented a collaborative effort made possible by the input and contributions of experts in the field of youth and civic engagement. The Report also addresses youth development issues around the world. The objective of the Report is to provide a basis for policy discussions around youth civic engagement in order to ensure that young people are able to participate fully and effectively in all aspects of the societies in which they live. At the international level, the World Bank has identified the exercise of active citizenship as one of the most important activities for a healthy transition to adulthood for both the youth of today and the next generation (UNDESA, 2015).

As indicated by UNDESA (2015), youth engagement may be considered an end in itself, but it is also a means to achieve other objectives and benefits in society. Promoting civic engagement as a component of youth work and youth action would positively result to personal development and improvement of the welfare of the youth. Moreover, interest in youth civic engagement is also linked to better public awareness of the rights of children and young people to have their voices heard. Increasing numbers of adults recognize the need to provide support and encourage youth participation and social action. It has been shown that the types of activities that students engage in are related to what they know about civic processes (Karliani et al., 2019). Similarly, attitudes toward civic engagement are associated with empathy, ethics, tolerance, and openness to others.

The apparent decline in the levels of civic and political engagement among young people worldwide and about the potential negative impact of this decline on the governance of society stimulated the interest in civic engagement. The reason for this focus on youth civic engagement was partly due to the assumption that when young people are involved in and connected to society, they are less likely to get involved in risky behavior and violence (UNDESA, 2015). In the light of these concepts, civic engagement has become one of the hallmarks of a democracy. For this reason, every Filipino should then be knowledgeable about civic engagement and should be encouraged to practice it. The youth, in particular, are at a stage in their lives during which they can make great contributions to their communities because they have the time and the energy for various civic activities, whether

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it is through their schools or through their peer groups. It is also the time when engagement in civic action critically contributes to their physical and psycho-social development (Zaff, Hart, Flanagan, Youniss, & Levine, 2010).

In terms of age differences in civic engagement, the study of Uka (2019) showed that there are significant age differences related to youth civic engagement where younger adolescents ages 12-14 had significantly higher levels of civic engagement than older adolescents ages 15-19. The study of Stefani, Prati, Tzankovaa , Ricci, Albanesi, & Cicognani (2021) showed that young female participants reported higher scores on online and civic participation, while male participants were more likely to report political and activist participation. This may imply that women tend to be socialized toward a gender role that is less oriented toward competition and more prone to cooperation, rule-abiding, and helping. Female role would be related to the desire to help others and to want to give something back to the community (Malin et al., 2015). Religious institutions are the most prominent set of associations within civil society. Adolescents volunteer more frequently in both religious and secular settings when they belong to a religious group, hold spirituality as a high value, or attend religious services regularly. People who are active in religious congregations tend to be happier and more civically engaged than either religiously unaffiliated adults or inactive members of religious groups (Pew Research Center, 2019). In families with higher socio-economic status, parents are more connected with social networks and institutions, thus knowing and valuing community organizations that involve adolescents, and assisting their children in accessing organized out-of-school activities. Moreover, more affluent families can better afford the costs associated with such participation (Lenzi, Vieno, Perkins, Santinello, Elgar, Morgan, & Mazzardis, 2012). Moreover, socio-economic inequality might lessen the equality of opportunity to engage civically based on available resources (Lancee and Van de Werfhorst, 2012; Karakoc, 2013).

In the context of Saint Mary's University, one of its mission is to *responsibly take the lead and participate in community-building*. This study was thus geared towards accomplishing its mission to a) provide opportunities for leading and being actively involved in building vibrant Christian communities (Community extension services); b) provide occasions for initiating and taking part in promoting CICM and social advocacies (CICM and social advocacies); and c) develop in the individual responsible citizenship and leadership skills (Responsible citizenship and leadership). This study aimed to determine the freshman college students' extent of civic knowledge, civic skills, and civic disposition on civic engagement. The profile of the respondents such as age, sex, socio-economic status, and religious affiliation was determined. The study further explored the differences in the civic knowledge, civic skills, and civic disposition of the respondents when grouped according to the profile variables.

Methodology

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This study aimed to determine the extent of knowledge, skills, and dispositions of the freshman college students on civic engagement in which findings of the study were used as bases in nurturing the students' civic engagement towards social entrepreneurship. The study employed the quantitative-qualitative research design. In the quantitative approach, descriptive-comparative technique was used to describe the extent of knowledge, skills, and dispositions of the senior students on civic engagement and to determine the relationship among variables. To attain this, a survey questionnaire was used. The study also used qualitative method to surface responses which may be used to provide in-depth discussion through open ended interview guide questions. This study was conducted at Saint Mary's University tertiary campus. Saint Mary's University is a premier CICM Catholic educational institution drawn into communion by the Wisdom of God, dedicated to the integral formation of persons exemplifying excellence, innovation, and passion for Christ's mission. SMU carries on the mission of integral human development by joyfully witnessing to Christ's mission, responsibly taking the lead and participating in community-building, relentlessly manifesting academic, personal and professional excellence, conscientiously strengthening communion, and steadfastly nurturing creativity and physical prowess. The respondents of the study were the first year college students from the School of Accountancy and Business, School of Health and Natural Sciences, School of Teacher Education and Humanities, and the School of Engineering, Architecture, and Information Technology. The respondents were selected through stratified random sampling. The research tool used for this study was adopted from the Civic Engagement Survey which was developed during the spring 2008 semester by the Southwest Minnesota State University (SMSU). SMSU faculty and staff initially deployed an online survey in April 2008. Graduating seniors were directed to complete this survey as part of their graduation requirements. Items on the survey measured students' demographics, their participation in volunteerism and other civic-oriented activities sponsored by SMSU, as well as their "civic-mindedness". Civic-mindedness was measured using the Civic Minded Graduate (CMG) Scale, adopted from the Center for Service and Learning at Indiana University – Purdue University at Indianapolis (IUPUI). The survey questionnaire was composed of two parts. Part 1 consisted of the respondents' demographics such as age, sex, economic status, and religious group. Part 2 was composed of statements which determined the respondents' extent of knowledge, skills, and dispositions on civic engagement. Part 3 consisted of open ended interview guide questions. The researchers crafted the survey questionnaire and the interview guide questions. After which, the approval of the research proposal and the floating of the guide questions were sought. Thereafter, the floating of the questionnaire was conducted. After the conduct of survey questionnaire, interview and focus group discussion were done. The profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, economic status, and religion was determined using frequency counts and percentage. The respondents' extent of knowledge, skills, and dispositions on civic engagement was determined using Mean and Standard Deviation. The difference in the respondents' extent of knowledge, skills, and dispositions on civic engagement was determined after the test of normalcy of data was conducted. Mann Whitney test was used to determine the difference in the students' extent of knowledge, skills, and dispositions on civic engagement when grouped according to sex and religious

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affiliation. Kruskal Wallis was used to determine the difference in the students' extent of knowledge, skills, and dispositions on civic engagement when grouped according to socio-economis status. Verbatim responses from the interview were coded and analyzed thematically.

There was no conflict of interest in conducting this study. There was no known risk in the respondents' participation to the study and there was no direct benefit to the respondents either. However, their contributions were valuable in determining the extent of civic knowledge, civic skills, and civic disposition on civic engagement. An Informed Consent Form was provided to the respondents. This study involved the conduct of interviews and focus group discussion. The schedule to conduct the study was set within the convenience of the participants. The respondents were selected as participants because they provided rich data for the study. The respondents' participation was voluntary and they could withdraw any time without explanation.

Results and Discussion

Results

Majority (254 or 66.8%) of the respondents were females. There were more Catholic respondents (166 or 43.7%) than non-Catholics. In terms of socio-economic status, 137 (36.1 %) belonged to families who can buy their needs and wants but have no savings.

Table 5
Freshman Students' Extent of Knowledge in Civic Engagement

	Mean	SD	QD
1. My experiences at SMU have helped me know a lot about opportunities to become involved in the community.	3.10	0.715	Moderate
2. Based on my experience at SMU, I would say that most other students know less about community organizations and volunteer opportunities than I do	2.30	0.757	Little
3. Through my experiences at SMU, I am very familiar with clubs and organizations that encourage and support community involvement for college students.	2.60	0.823	Moderate
4. My education experience at SMU has given me the professional knowledge and skills that I need to help address community issues.	3.06	0.682	Moderate
5. After being a student at SMU, I feel confident that I will be able to apply what I have learned in my classes to solve real problems in society.	3.12	0.727	Moderate
6. My experiences at SMU have enabled me to plan or help implement an initiative that improves the community.	2.96	0.716	Moderate
7. My experiences at SMU have prepared me to write a letter to the newspaper or community leaders about a community issue.	2.14	0.815	Little
8. My education at SMU has made me aware of a number of community issues that need to be addressed	2.96	0.735	Moderate
9. My education at SMU has motivated me to stay up to date on the current political issues in the community	2.80	0.824	Moderate

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Overall Mean	2.78	0.499	Moderate
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Table 5 shows the extent of freshman students' extent of knowledge in civic engagement . As indicated by the overall mean (Mean= 2.78), the freshman students knowledge of civic engagement is only to a moderate extent. The highest mean is on the students' experiences at SMU which have enabled them to plan or help implement an initiative that improves the community (Mean = 2.96) while the lowest mean shows the students' experiences at SMU have prepared them to write a letter to the newspaper or community leaders about a community issue (Mean=2.14).

Table 6
Freshman Students' Extent of Skills in Civic Engagement

	Mean	SD	QD
1. My experiences at SMU have helped make me a good listener, even when peoples' opinions are different from mine.	3.37	0.647	Moderate
2. My SMU education has prepared me to listen to others and understand their perspective on controversial issues.	3.20	0.701	Moderate
3. My experiences at SMU have helped me realize that I prefer to work in settings in which I interact with people who are different from me	2.86	0.798	Moderate
4. My SMU education has helped me appreciate how my community is enriched by having some cultural or ethnic diversity.	3.31	0.681	Moderate
5. My experiences at SMU have helped me develop my ability to respond to others with empathy, regardless of their backgrounds.	3.28	0.691	Moderate
6. As a result of my experiences at SMU, other students who know me well would describe me as a person who can discuss controversial social issues with civility and respect.	2.77	0.797	Moderate
7. My experiences at SMU have helped me realize that when members of my group disagree on how to solve a problem, I like to try to build consensus.	2.79	0.712	Moderate
8. When discussing controversial social issues at SMU, I have often been able to persuade others to agree with my point of view.	2.49	0.785	Little
Overall mean	3.00	0.510	Moderate

Table 6 presents the freshman students' extent of skills in civic engagement. As shown in the overall mean, the skills in civic engagement of the freshman students is only to a moderate extent (mean=3.00). The highest mean indicates that the students experiences at SMU have helped make them a good listener, even when peoples' opinions are different from their opinion (Mean=3.37). The lowest mean shows that, when students discuss controversial social issues at SMU, the students have often been able to persuade others to agree with their point of view (Mean=2.49).

Table 7
Freshman Students' Extent of Disposition in Civic Engagement

	Mean	SD	QD
1. My SMU experiences helped me to realize that I like to be involved in addressing community issues.	2.72	0.781	Moderate

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2. My SMU experiences have helped me develop my sense of who I am, which now includes a sincere desire to be of service to others.	3.03	0.763	Moderate
3. Based on my experiences at SMU, I would say that the main purposes of work are to improve society through my career.	3.19	0.704	Moderate
4. My education at SMU has increased my confidence that I can contribute to improving life in my community.	3.07	0.838	Moderate
5. My SMU education has convinced me that social problems are not too complex for me to help solve.	3.01	0.772	Moderate
6. Because of my experiences at SMU, I believe that having an impact on community problems is within my reach.	2.60	0.748	Moderate
7. As a result of my experiences at SMU, I want to dedicate my career to improving society.	2.76	0.714	Moderate
8. Because of the experiences I had at SMU, I feel a deep conviction in my career goals to achieve purposes that are beyond my own self-interest	3.15	0.725	Moderate
9. I believe that I have a responsibility to use the knowledge I have gained at SMU to serve others.	3.08	0.758	Moderate
Overall mean	2.95	0.518	Moderate

Table 7 presents the freshman students' extent of disposition in civic engagement. As shown in the overall mean (Mean=2.95), the students' disposition in civic engagement is only to a moderate extent. The highest mean indicates that, based on students' experiences at SMU, they opined that the main purposes of work are to improve society through their career (Mean=3.19). The lowest mean shows that, because of the students' experiences at SMU, they believe that having an impact on community problems is within their reach (Mean = 2.60).

Table 8
Difference in the Extent of knowledge and skills on Civic Engagement when grouped in terms of Sex

	SEX	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	Wilcoxon W	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
Knowledge	Male	185.23	14769	21672	-0.094	0.925
	Female	186.35				
Skills	Male	169.96	12982.5	19885.5	-1.85	0.064
	Female	191.98				
Disposition	Male	170.68	13066	19969	-1.873	0.061
	Female	193.06				

Table 8 shows the difference in the students' extent of knowledge and skills on civic engagement when grouped in terms of sex. As shown in the p values on knowledge (0.925), skills (0.064), and disposition (0.061), there is no significant difference in the students' extent of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement when grouped in terms of sex as indicated by the p values greater than 0.05. This means that the students' extent of knowledge and skills on civic engagement are statistically the same.

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Table 9

Difference in the Extent of knowledge and skills on Civic Engagement when grouped in terms of Religious Affiliation

	Religious Affiliation	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	Wilcoxon W	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
Knowledge	Catholic	127.43	6485.5	9971.5	-0.755	0.45
	Non-Catholic	120.14				
Skills	Catholic	126.11	6460	9946	-0.654	0.513
	Non-Catholic	119.83				
Disposition	Catholic	128.91	6239.5	9725.5	-1.215	0.224
	Non-Catholic	117.17				

Table 9 shows the difference in the students' extent of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement when grouped in terms of religious affiliation. As shown in the p values on knowledge (0.45), skills (0.513), and disposition (0.224), there is no significant difference in the students' extent of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement when grouped in terms of religious affiliation as indicated by the p values greater than 0.05. This means that the students' extent of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement are statistically the same.

Table 10

Difference in the Extent of knowledge, skills, and disposition on Civic Engagement when grouped in terms of Socio-economic status

	SES	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis H	df	Asymp. Sig.
Knowledge	My family can buy our needs but no savings	122.7	42.142	3	0.001
	My family can buy our needs and have savings	127.57			
	My family can buy our needs and wants but no savings	176.86			
	My family can buy our needs and wants and have savings	215.98			
Skills	My family can buy our needs but no savings	112.97	13.727	3	0.003
	My family can buy our needs and have savings	147.52			
	My family can buy our needs and wants but no savings	178.51			
	My family can buy our needs and wants and have savings	185.12			

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Disposition	My family can buy our needs but no savings	131.9	18.276	3	0.001
	My family can buy our needs and have savings	144.16			
	My family can buy our needs and wants but no savings	171.55			
	My family can buy our needs and wants and have savings	201.78			

Table 10 shows the difference in the students' extent of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement when grouped in terms of Socio-economic status. As shown in the p values on knowledge (0.001), Skills (0.003), and disposition (0.001), there is significant difference in the students' extent of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement when grouped in terms of socio-economic status as indicated by the p values lesser than 0.05. This means that the students' extent of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement is significantly different.

Discussion

Civic engagement refers to the active participation of individuals in the community to promote the common good. It includes activities such as voting, volunteering, advocating for social justice, and engaging in public discourse. Findings in this study indicate that the freshman students' knowledge of civic engagement is only to a moderate extent. In the context of Saint Mary's University, foremost among the students' civic engagement is focused on their experiences at SMU which have enabled them to plan or help implement an initiative that improves the community. Similarly, the skills in civic engagement of the freshman students is only to a moderate extent. Primarily, this is shown in the students' experiences at SMU which have helped make them good listener, even when peoples' opinions are different from their opinion. Moreover, the freshman students' extent of disposition in civic engagement is only to a moderate extent. This shows that, based on students' experiences at SMU, they opined that the main purposes of work are to improve society through their career.

Civic engagement is essential to the health of communities inasmuch as through engagement in civic activities, people from diverse backgrounds come together to address community problems. Though the level of civic engagement among students is good, there is a need to introduce as well as increase activities that may augment students' engagement. As stated in the study of Hylton (2018), increased civic literacy and social empathy correlate to higher rates of civic engagement among university students. Many university activities such as co-curricular and extra curricular activities and service-learning opportunities aim at increasing civic engagement among college students. These initiatives aim to improve students' knowledge and understanding of civic engagement and encourage them to become active citizens. As shown in the study of Pevzner, Shaydorova, & Taha (2021), these activities change the students' understanding and perception of leadership, volunteering and participation in the life of the local community, choice of a future profession, effective use of leisure, a sense of involvement and belonging to society, compliance with rules and laws, and

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democracy values. Freshman students may have varying levels of knowledge on civic engagement depending on their prior experiences and exposure to civic engagement. It is worth noting that civic engagement is a complex topic that involves a wide range of issues and challenges, including political polarization, social justice, and inequality. Therefore, it is important to provide students programs and activities to stay informed about current events and social issues in order to become more engaged citizens (Torney-Purta, Cabrera, Roohr, Liu, & Rios (2015).

Educational institutions play significant role in the development of civic engagement among students. Educational programs focused on values, positions, and critical thinking skills which enable young people to become active and independent participants of civil and political activities. The scope of students' involvement in civic engagement often differ significantly in terms of sex, religious affiliation and socio-economic status (Pevzner, Shaydorova, & Taha, 2021). However, the findings in this study show that there is no significant difference in the students' extent of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement when grouped in terms of sex. This is corroborated by the study of Zabolotna & Pidhaietska (2021) which found that gender, religious involvement, personality type, and family's political involvement do not directly influence the students' civic engagement. However, the findings of this study is contradictory to the results in the study of Engberg and Davidson (2016) which linked college involvement in curricular and co-curricular opportunities focused on learning about difference, global issues, and leadership or service opportunities. As stated by Engberg and Davidson (2016), these activities highlight the influence of civic engagement in the development of the students' cognitive, intrapersonal, and interpersonal aspects. Moreover, the study found that female college students were more likely than male students to participate in community service or service learning activities and to report higher levels of social responsibility and empathy as a result of their participation. It is important to note, however, that gender is a complex and multifaceted concept, and other factors such as race, ethnicity, and sexual orientation may also influence students' level of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement. In summary, while limited research suggests that female college freshmen may be more likely than male students to participate in community service and to have positive attitudes toward civic engagement, further research is needed to fully understand the relationship between sex and civic engagement among college freshmen.

In terms of religious affiliation, the findings of the study shows there is no significant difference in the students' extent of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement when grouped in terms of religious affiliation. This is corroborated by the study of Zabolotna & Pidhaietska (2021) which found that gender, religious involvement, personality type, and family's political involvement do not directly influence the students' civic engagement. However, a study by the Higher Education Research Institute at UCLA found that in 2019, college freshmen who identified as Protestant or Catholic were more likely to report having participated in community service than those who identified as non-religious or as members of other religions. Another study by the National Study of Learning, Voting, and Engagement found that college students who attended religious services at least once a month were more likely to vote in the 2018 midterm elections than those who did not attend religious services.

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However, the study did not explore the relationship between religious affiliation and civic engagement more broadly. Overall, while limited research suggests that college freshmen who identify as Protestant or Catholic may be more likely to participate in community service, further research is needed to fully understand the relationship between religious affiliation and civic engagement among college freshmen. It is important to note that religious affiliation is a complex and multifaceted concept, and other factors such as religious practices, beliefs, and values may also influence students' level of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement. In summary, while limited research suggests that college freshmen who identify as Protestant or Catholic may be more likely to participate in community service, further research is needed to fully understand the relationship between religious affiliation and civic engagement among college freshmen.

In terms of socio-economic status, findings in this study show that there is significant difference in the students' extent of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement when grouped in terms of socio-economic status. Research on the relationship between socioeconomic status (SES) and college freshmen's level of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement is relatively more extensive. The findings of this study show that college students from lower SES backgrounds are less likely to be engaged in civic activities and to have lower levels of civic knowledge and skills. This is affirmed in the study by the Higher Education Research Institute at UCLA found that in 2019 which found that college freshmen from families with lower incomes and first-generation college students were less likely to report participating in community service than their peers from higher income families and those whose parents had college degrees. Another study by the National Study of Learning, Voting, and Engagement found that in the 2018 midterm elections, college students from lower income families were less likely to vote than their peers from higher income families. In terms of skills and disposition, a study by the American Council on Education found that college students from lower income families and those who were the first in their families to attend college reported lower levels of social responsibility and empathy, even after controlling for demographic factors. Overall, research suggests that college freshmen from lower SES backgrounds may be less likely to participate in civic activities and to have lower levels of civic knowledge, skills, and disposition than their peers from higher SES backgrounds. This may be due to a range of factors, such as differences in access to civic education, opportunities for community engagement, and social networks that facilitate civic participation. It is important to note, however, that SES is a complex and multifaceted concept, and other factors such as race, ethnicity, and gender may also influence students' level of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement. In summary, research suggests that college freshmen from lower SES backgrounds may be less likely to participate in civic activities and to have lower levels of civic knowledge, skills, and disposition than their peers from higher SES backgrounds. Further research is needed to better understand the relationship between SES and civic engagement among college freshmen, as well as to identify effective strategies for promoting civic engagement among students from lower SES backgrounds.

Conclusion

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In the light of the findings, this study concludes that the freshman students' extent of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement is moderate which indicate a need to strengthen this particular concern. Moreover, socio-economic status affect the freshman students' extent of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn, this study recommends that the University provides activities that will help strengthen students' extent of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement. It is equally important that the University continue to nurture the students' extent of knowledge, skills, and disposition on civic engagement across socio-economic status through entrepreneurial activities that will respond to the socio-economic gap.

References

- Bermudez, A. (2012) Youth civic engagement: Decline or transformation? A critical review. *Journal of Moral Education*, 41(4), 529-542, DOI: [10.1080/03057240.2012.732296](https://doi.org/10.1080/03057240.2012.732296)
- Engberg, M. E., & Davidson, L. M. (2016). Students' precollege engagement and the development of a global perspective. *Journal of The First-Year Experience & Students in Transition*, 28(1), 49-70.
- Higher Educational Research(2019). The 2019 CIRP Freshman Survey. <https://heri.ucla.edu/>
- Hylton, M. E. (2018). The role of civic literacy and social empathy on rates of civic engagement among university students. *Journal of Higher Education Outreach and Engagement*, 22(1), 87-106.
- Lancee, B., Van de Werfhorst, H. G. (2012). Income inequality and participation: A comparison of 24 European Countries. *Social Science Research*, 41, 1166–1178.
- Lenzi, M., Vieno, A., Santinello, M., & Nation, M. (2014). The role played by the family in shaping early and middle adolescent civic responsibility. *The Journal of Early Adolescence* 34(2). DOI:10.1177/0272431613485822
- Malin, H., Han, H., & Liauw, I. (2017). Civic purpose in late adolescence: Factors that prevent decline in civic engagement after high school. *Developmental Psychology*, 53(7), 1384.
- National Study on Voting, Learning, and Engagement (2018). <https://ira.virginia.edu/data-analytics/survey-data/nslve>
- Owusu-Agyeman, Y., & Fourie-Malherbe, M. (2021). Students as partners in the promotion of civic engagement in higher education. *Studies in Higher Education*, 46(6), 1241-1255.

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Pevzner, M., Shaydorova, N., & Taha, F. (2021). Development Of Social Activity And Civic Engagement Among Israeli Students. *European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences*.

Pew Research Center (2019). Religion's relationship to happiness, civic engagement and health around the world.

<https://www.pewresearch.org/religion/2019/01/31/religions-relationship-to-happiness-civic-engagement-and-health-around-the-world/>

Sieriakova, I., & Kokoza, G. (2019). Civic Education in Ukraine: A Qualitative Study of Students' Experiences of Civic Engagement. *Advanced Education*, 13, 36-43.

Torney-Purta, J., Cabrera, J. C., Roohr, K. C., Liu, O. L., & Rios, J. A. (2015). Assessing civic competency and engagement in higher education: Research background, frameworks, and directions for next-generation assessment. *ETS Research Report Series*, 2015(2), 1-48.

Zabolotna, O., & Pidhaietska, A. (2021). Students' civic engagement in Ukraine and Canada: a comparative analysis. *Multidisciplinary Journal for Education, Social and Technological Sciences*, 8(1), 85-101.

